

D7.7 First report on dissemination

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
BOKU	University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences
BUT	Białystok University of Technology
CDUE	Communication, dissemination, upscaling and exploitation
CU	Charles University
EMU	Estonian University of Applied Sciences
HAW	Hamburg University of Applied Sciences
IAMO	Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies
IGAR	Institute of Geography of the Romanian Academy
LU	University of Latvia
SUA	Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra
T	Task
UC	University of Coimbra
UCPH	University of Copenhagen
UNIBO	University of Bologna
WP	Work package

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Executive Summary

This First Report on dissemination pertains to deliverable D7.7 in Task 7.4 within the WP 7 Information, Communication, Upscaling, and Capacity-Building of the Europe-LAND project under Grant Agreement No. 101081307.

It is intended to provide a detailed report of the dissemination and communication actions carried out by partners over the first 24 months of the project duration (June 2023 to May 2025). It is in line with the continuous reporting to the European Commission.

This report is due to be delivered in May 2025 (M24) and will be updated one more time in the course of the project in month 48 (D7.8).

For any comments on this CDUE-Plan, please contact the Project Coordinator:

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1. Introduction

Within the Europe-LAND project, work package 7 aims to generate visibility and awareness of the project and its activities as well as to engage and empower project stakeholders to build upon the outcomes in the longer term. The deliverable D7.1 CDUE-Plan and its update D7.2 lay out a strategy for the communication, dissemination, upscaling and exploitation of the project work, forming the basis for all work carried out within the Work Package. This deliverable, D7.7 first report on dissemination, is a subsequent report of all dissemination and communication work carried out by all partners over the first 24 months of the project, ranging from 1st June 2023 to 30th May 2025. It is in line with the continuous reporting system in the EU portal, but offers additional information for each action as well as a categorization according to the conceptual frame of the CDUE-Plan.

Within the Grant Agreement, this D7.7 was envisioned to contain a detailed plan of dissemination activities. However, to better reflect the full extent of the work carried out and also in line with the aforementioned continuous reporting, communication activities as well as scientific works are also included, with dedicated chapters and detailed descriptions for each.

The report is structured into five chapters, the first being the introduction. Chapter two describes the dissemination activities carried out within the reported period, chapter three the communication activities, and chapter four scientific work. Chapter five offers some conclusions from the report.

Whenever feasible, for each action the intended stakeholder groups and the reached audience are indicated. Further information is provided where possible for activities not subject to further reporting. For many of the events reported within 3.1, separate reports are or will be available in the form of further deliverables. As such, the report on these activities is kept minimal.

2. Dissemination activities

Dissemination refers to the sharing of project outputs with the identified stakeholder groups and a broader audience, to facilitate the uptake by the appropriate actors. The Europe-LAND project defined a variety of dissemination activities which would be pursued over the course of the project, to reach various stakeholder groups. A detailed plan is laid out in D7.1 CDUE-Plan and its subsequent yearly updates (D7.2, 7.3, 7.4). The following chapters detail the various dissemination activities as they were implemented by project partners over the first 24 months. Each activity has additionally been reported to the European Commission via the continuous reporting system in the portal.

2.1 Participation in external conferences and meetings

Within the first 24 months of the project, Europe-LAND partners attended 29 conferences and external meetings. They are briefly described below.

ECCA2023 – 19.-21.06.2023 (HAW)

Jasmin Röseler (HAW Hamburg) attended the conference and presented the project during a session titled "Nature-based Solutions: Evaluation and Implementation". <https://www.ecca2023.eu/>

Audience: 40

Audience type: Research communities, national authorities

World Symposium of Climate Change and Sustainable Development Centres - 29.-30.06.2023 (HAW)

Franziska Wolf (HAW Hamburg) presented the project at the symposium.

Audience: 30

Audience type: Research communities

AGROKOMPLEX 2023 - 17.-20.08.2023 (SUA)

Danka Moravčíková (SUA) presented insights into the new project Europe-LAND.

Audience: 50

Audience type: National authorities, Research communities, Industry, business partners

International Conference on Agriculture and Life Science (ICOALS IV) - 1.-3.11.2023 (IAMO)

Daniel Müller (IAMO) delivered a keynote speech, representing the Europe-LAND project.

Audience: 200

Audience type: Research communities, National authorities, Regional authorities

Baltic University Program symposium - 7.-8.11.2023 (LU)

The LU team delivered a presentation of land use modelling tools.

Audience: 50 online

Audience type: Research communities, Regional authorities, Civil society

First Interim Meeting Regional Expert Advisory Working Group on Climate Change Adaptation in Agriculture (REAWAG) - 22.-24.11.2023 (IAMO)

Daniel Müller (IAMO) attended the event, representing the Europe-LAND project. He delivered a keynote speech. More information can be found under: <https://seerural.org/news/first-meeting-of-reawg-on-the-climate-change-adaptation-in-agriculture/>

Audience: 30

Audience type: Research communities, National authorities, Regional authorities

Hajnówka Odnowa project meeting - 12.01.2024 (BUT)

The BUT team attended the project meeting, fostering regional synergies.

Audience: 23

Audience type: Local authorities, Research communities, Regional authorities

82nd International Scientific Conference of the University of Latvia - 16.02.2024 (LU)

The LU Europe-LAND team hosted a session entitled “Changes in the dynamics of bog development under the influence of natural conditions and human activity”

Audience: 64

Audience type: Research communities, local authorities, NGOs

AAG2024, Honolulu, Hawaii - 16-20.04.2024 (IGAR)

Mihaela Sima (IGAR) attended the Annual Meeting of the American Association of Geographers, where she organised a Europe-LAND session entitled “Experiences in Co-creating Sustainability Strategies across Regions and Cultures using Living Labs and Participatory Methodologies” and presented an oral paper on “Stakeholders’ engagement in climate change and land management. Lessons learnt from the Lower Danube Basin, Romania”, Link:<https://www.aag.org/events/aag2024/>

Audience: 50 in the session, the conference had around 4,000 participants

Audience type: Research communities

Baltic University Programme (BUP) International Symposium - 21.-23.04.2024 (BUT)

Alicja Antochow (BUT) presented a poster related to the Europe-LAND project.

Audience: 100

Audience type: Research communities

10th NGM (Nordic Geographer's Meeting) in Copenhagen - 24.-27.06.2024 (CU)

Khalil Gholamnia (CU) attended the conference and presented his work entitled “Predicting Future Land Use and Cover Changes in the Krkonoše Mts. National Park Using Machine Learning and Markov Chain Modelling” (authors of the presentation Khalil Gholamnia, Lucie Kupková).

Audience: 18

Audience type: Research communities

IAMO Forum 2024 - 26.06.2024 (HAW, IAMO, EMU, SUA)

Jasmin Röseler (HAW) hosted a specialized session titled "Sustainable land-use and land management in the EU and beyond – first lessons from the Horizon Europe project Europe-LAND". Clemens Jänicke (IAMO), Prof Anton Shkaruba (EMU) and Prof Alexander Fehér (SUA) contributed presentations on the ongoing work in WP2, 4 and 5.

Audience: 63

Audience type: Research communities, authorities

35th International Geographical Congress (IGU) in Dublin, 2024 - 24.-30.08.2024 (CU, IGAR, SUA, BOKU)

A special session was proposed for the International Geographical Union Congress in Dublin, 24-30 August 2024. The session is entitled “Land use and land management strategies for climate change adaptation and biodiversity conservation” (Session chairs: Mihaela Sima and Lucie Kupková). The following presentation of the IGAR team was presented: The implication of land governance in land use/cover (LU/LC) dynamics in the Romanian Plain (Authors: Mihaela Sima, Ana-Elena Urşanu

(Popovici), Gheorghe Kucsicsa, Dan Bălteanu, Ines Grigorescu, Monica Dumitrașcu). Europe-Land partners from Austria, Czechia and Slovakia also presented during the session. Team of CU presented contribution entitled: "Long-Term Vegetation Cover Changes in the Central European Tundra: Management Practice and Biodiversity" (authors: Lucie Kupková, Tomáš Hejda Markéta Potůčková, Lucie Červená, Jakub Lysák, Stanislav Březina, Zábaj Hrázský, Zdeněk Boudný).

Audience: 30

Audience type: Research communities, international organizations.

Earth Observation Colloquium - 04.11.2024 (IAMO)

Clemens Jänicke (IAMO) gave a 90 min presentation titled "An EU-wide farm typology from field- and farm-level land use data".

Audience: 15, in presence and online

Audience type: Research communities

GLP's 5th Open Science Meeting: Pathways to Sustainable and just land systems - 4.-8.11.2024 (UC)

Miguel Moreira (UC) presented attended the meeting in Oaxaca, Mexico and held a presentation entitled "Engagement of multi-level stakeholders in sustainable land use management: The Castro Verde case study (Portugal)". <https://event.fourwaves.com/osm2024/pages>.

Audience: 800 at the conference, 25 in the session

Audience type: Research communities

Slovak and Czech Sociological Days 2024 – 10.-13.09.2024 (SUA)

The SUA team delivered a presentation titled "Land-Use in the Context of Climate Change: sociological aspects of interdisciplinary research in project Europe-LAND", connected to the Task 5.1 and 5.2.

Audience: 95

Audience type: Research communities, other

International Scientific Conference Resilient and Sustainable Economies – 11.-25.09.2024 (BUT)

Paper presentation entitled: Classification and assessment of policy instruments related to sustainable land-use decisions. More information is available at:

https://konferencjkrsg.uwb.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/RSE_2024_Program-20240925.pdf

Audience: 106

Audience type: Research communities, Regional authorities, Local authorities.

Landscape 2024, Berlin - 16.-20.09.2025 (BOKU)

Claudine Egger (BOKU) attended the Landscape 2024 in Berlin, Germany. In the session "Modelling farmers' decision-making to investigate and enhance transformation of agroecosystems", she gave the oral presentation "Effects of extreme events on farmers' decision-making in a pre-alpine region in Austria".

Audience type: Research communities

11th National IPBES forum, Germany - 06.11.2024 (HAW)

Prof Walter Leal (HAW), coordinator of the project, attended the national IPBES forum in Bonn, representing the project.

Audience: 100

Audience type: Research communities, Authorities

COP29 Baku 2024 – 11.-17.11.2024 (ATh)

The ATh team attended COP29. At the EU pavilion, Europe-LAND was part of the projects presentation.

Audience: more than 10,000 people visited the EU pavilion

Audience type: Research communities, international organizations, Civil society

Workshop on climate change and transition to sustainable agriculture in candidate countries - 21.11.2024 (IAMO)

Enlargement workshop with contribution of Daniel Müller about the Western Balkan.

Audience: 25

Audience type: EU institutions, DG Agri, Policy makers

MedGU Barcelona – 25.-28.11.2024 (CU)

CU (Khalil Gholamnia) had oral presentation on the meeting of Mediterranean Geosciences Union entitled: “Modeling Future Land Use/Land Cover Patterns in the Krkonoše Mts. National Park Using Machine Learning Classification and CLUE-S Model” (authors of the presentation Khalil Gholamnia, Lucie Kupková).

Audience: 20

Audience type: Research communities

Green Deal 2024 Conference - 27.11.2024 (LU)

The LU team participated in the conference with a presentation of land use changes in protected areas.

Audience: 30 on-site, 25 online

Audience type: Research communities, EU institutions, Regional authorities

Innovations for healthy landscapes and responsible farmers in Slovakia – 07.11.2024 (SUA)

Promotion of the project and discussion at the national event Innovations for healthy landscapes and responsible farmers in Slovakia.

Audience: 75

Audience type: Research communities, land users, policy makers

Preparation of the new agri-policy and adaptation of the Strategic Plan of the Common Agricultural Policy in Slovakia – 10.12.2024 (SUA)

Promotion of the project and discussion at the national event Preparation of the new agri-policy and adaptation of the Strategic Plan of the Common Agricultural Policy in Slovakia.

Audience: 110

Audience type: land users

EU Family Meeting 2025 in Hamburg - 24.03.2025 (HAW)

Organized by the Senate Chancellery of the Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg, the City Hall meeting on 25 March 2025 was attended by approx. 150 persons from local government, authorities, and further stakeholders from science, NGOs, and businesses who informed themselves about EU funding opportunities, received an overview of Hamburg's EU funded projects and learned about some future developments related to EU funding environments.

Audience: 150

Audience type: local authorities, industry, business partners, research communities

ISPRS Geospatial Week 2025 in Dubai - 10.04.2025(CU)

A poster related to the Krkonoše Mountains case study “Monitoring Invasive and Expansive Species in the Krkonoše Mountains Using Multitemporal UAV Data and Botanical Research” (Kupková L., Červená L., Lysák J., Hrázský Z., Potůčková M., Šrollerů A., Novotná B., Vítková M., Pergl J., Čuda J., Kolombová N., Kušková K., Kutlvašr J., Perglová I., Sádlo J., Vitek V., Pyšek P.) was presented.

Audience: 600

Audience type: Research communities

IGU Thematic Conference 2025 in Cairo - 12.04.2025 (CU, IGAR)

The presentation entitled “Landscape Transformation in Czechia Over the Last 30 Years: Diversity of Changes at Two Spatial Levels” (Lucie Kupková & Zdeněk Boudný) was presented (CU).

Mihaela Sima and Ana Ursanu (IGAR team) attended the meeting and presented the following presentations at the sessions organized by the Land Use/Land Cover Change Commission:

“Challenges in sustainable land use in Romania in the context of climate change: Insights from a living lab approach in Europe-LAND project”, Authors: Mihaela SIMA, Dan BĂLTEANU, Gheorghe KUCSICSA, Ines GRIGORESCU, Elena Ana URŞANU, Marius BÎRSAN, Nicoleta DAMIAN, Laura Lupu, Alexandra VRÎNCEANU, Monica DUMITRAŞCU and “Developing a baseline scenario for future changes in agricultural land in Romania (2050) using the CLUE-S model”, authors: Elena Ana URŞANU, Gheorghe KUSICSA, Mihaela SIMA, Ines GRIGORESCU, Monica DUMITRAŞCU, Dan BĂLTEANU.

Audience: 50 in sessions, over 300 at the conference

Audience type: Research communities

2.2 Education and training events

Educating and training future experts and land users as well as internal capacity building are essential to maximize the impact of the Europe-LAND project. Over the first two years of the project, partners participated in eight education and training events, detailed below.

Lecture "Agriculture and SDGs" – 25.10.2023 (HAW)

Jasmin Röseler (HAW) gave a guest lecture on the correlation between agriculture and the sustainable development goals (SDGs) for Bachelor students of Ecotrophology at the University of Applied Sciences in Hamburg.

Students: 20

Audience type: Research communities

"Enhancing climate education through blended and online learning technologies", Erasmus+ CBHE project CLIMED training; information session about relevant projects run at EMU - 04.10.2024 (EMU)

A session on a training for Ukrainian educators and researchers on relevant projects involving EMU; <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/15DMAqzv3g/>

Audience: 25

Audience type: Research communities, Research authorities

Research seminar for doctoral students of Mongolian University of Life Sciences by Prof. Anton Shkaruba - 14.10.2024 (EMU)

A part of training session by Prof. Anton Shkaruba on Erasmus+ mobility exchange trip to a partner university; <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1BHDJrJ67v1/>

Audience: 22

Audience type: Research communities

Departmental research seminar - 23.10.2024 (EMU)

An update about the project implementation progress on a regular departmental research seminar; <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1GPQCmjGda/>

Audience: 31

Audience type: Research communities

Research seminar "Applications of remote sensing in agriculture and environmental monitoring in Estonia" by Prof. Kalev Sepp at the National Chung Hsing University (NCHU), Taiwan - 08.11.2024 (EMU)

Training session and discussion; presentations of relevant research activities at the Department, including LAND Europe project, <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/19eotSpFPj/>

Audience: 46

Audience type: Research communities, Research authorities

WSDTID (World sustainable development teach-in day) 2024 - 04.12.2024 (HAW)

Jasmin Röseler (HAW Hamburg) participated with a presentation titled "Sustainable land use and its contributions to the SDGs"

Audience: 131

Audience type: Research communities

Annual Session of the Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy – 06.12.2024 (IGAR)

Mihaela Sima presented a plenary lecture entitled „Living Lab: Challenges in sustainable land management in Romania in the context of climate change. The experience of a participatory approach in the Horizon Europe-LAND project“.

Audience: 75

Audience type: Research community

Section seminar of the University of Copenhagen – 2024 (UCPH)

UCPH project team delivered a presentation on Danish afforestation politics, mapping of potential locations for afforestation and the cost of converting the farmland to forest at an internal section seminar.

Audience type: Research communities

2.3 clustering activities and other scientific collaborations

Collaboration with other projects and experts in the field of land use and land management, as well as biodiversity, climate change and other project-related fields is another important aspect of dissemination activities. Exchanging knowledge, and fostering synergies helps strengthen internal capacities as well as maximize outreach. Europe-LAND partners participated in five such clustering activities over the first 24 months.

Mission Adaptation Community Event: Second Mission Projects Seminar - 15.10.2024 (HAW)

HAW attended to represent EL as a "friend of the mission" and participated in the networking breakout sessions.

Audience: 60

Audience type: EU institutions, Research communities

Seminar on land use challenges for climate change – 14.10.2024 (UC)

National seminar titled "challenges in land use management for climate change response", organised under the scope of the WP3 objectives. It was attended by target stakeholders and general audience.

Audience: 13

Audience type: National authorities, Regional authorities, Civil society

MIP4Adapt Communication Group Winter Meeting - 30.01.2025 (HAW)

Participation of the communication manager (HAW) of the project in the meeting.

Audience: 30

Audience type: Research communities, EU institutions

Wetlands and Blue Carbon - CINEA study - 04.02.2025 (HAW)

The workshop aims at improving the knowledge base to improve the accuracy and completeness of the EU Member States (MS) greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories. Specifically, CINEA is trying to understand the current status of all reporting categories of wetlands, across all EU MS. The EU also trying to understand if and how EU MS could create “blue carbon” GHG inventories. It also seeks to build an EU wide monitoring roadmap.

Audience: -

Audience type: EU institutions, research communities

Gremienmesse Winter 2025 at HAW - 04.04.2025 (HAW)

The HAW Hamburg team presented the Europe-LAND project at an internally organized fair of HAW projects and committees.

Audience: 250

Audience type: Research communities

3. Communication activities

Communication, besides dissemination, is another important aspect of the work carried out within WP7 of the Europe-LAND project. It refers to informing and engaging stakeholders as well as the general public about the project, ongoing activities as well as outputs, with the aim to raise awareness and visibility of the project and its relevance, to promote project outcomes and improve impact. The communication strategy within the D7.1 CDUE-Plan employs a variety of tools and channels for communication, to reach different stakeholder groups as well as traditional media and the general public. The following chapters detail the communication activities performed by Europe-LAND partners over the first 24 months of the project. Each activity was also reported to the European Commission via the continuous reporting system in the portal.

3.1 events organized by the project

Organizing events for specific target audiences is an important tool to reach the intended stakeholders with targeted information to maximize the relevance of the inputs. Events are also a crucial part of the Europe-LAND methodology. As such, many events, workshops and other events were already anticipated within the Grant Agreement or later defined as part of the methodological framework of several of the WPs. This chapter focuses on such events and their conceptual frame.

Capacity building seminars

In the frame of WP6 T6.3, a series of capacity building seminars are being organized in cooperation with each WP. Each seminar is aimed at specific target audiences, depending on the content. An in-depth report on all capacity building seminars will be published as D6.6 in M45. The following list will briefly name the capacity building seminars hosted thus far.

“Sustainable land use and land management in the EU and beyond – first lessons from the Horizon Europe project Europe-LAND”, 27.06.2024 in Halle (Saale), Germany (HAW, IAMO, EMU, SUA)

“Land use and land management strategies for climate change and biodiversity conservation”, 29.08.2024 in Dublin, Ireland (IGAR, SUA, BOKU, CU)

“Leveraging data from the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) for research”, 19.-21.02.2025 in Hamburg, Germany (UCPH, IAMO, HAW)

“Prospective trends in the mapping of future expected land use and land cover patterns”, 24.04.2025 online (LU, CU, IGAR)

Expert webinar series

Task 7.3 the strategic stakeholder engagement of the Europe-LAND project proposed an expert webinar series consisting of 6 webinars within the first year of the project, establishing the role of the project and engaging stakeholders early on. These 6 expert webinars were listed below, reaching a total of 425 participants.

“Towards Sustainable Land-use Strategies in the Context of Climate Change and Biodiversity Challenges in Europe - Introducing the Horizon Europe project Europe-LAND”, 26.10.2023

“Harmonization of European land use data – challenges and opportunities”, 20.11.2023

“Towards sustainable European land-use strategies – The importance of participatory approaches”, 23.01.2024

“Mapping future land-use and land cover patterns – the Europe-LAND approach”, 15.02.2024

“In the spotlight: the Europe-LAND case studies”, 14.03.2024

“Exploring the potential of Telecoupling for improving European land management”, 18.04.2024

After the successful conclusion of the 6 expert webinars in the first project year, the consortium decided to continue the format and to periodically organize expert webinars. By the time of this deliverable, an additional 3 webinars have been hosted so far.

“Introducing the Europe-LAND Toolbox”, 30.05.2024

“Towards an interactive digital Toolbox on sustainable land-use”, 29.01.2025

“Peatlands Perspectives: Latest Data on Distribution, Agricultural Practices and Emission Factors in the EU”, 11.04.2025

Yearly Science EU Policy Dialogue

Another participatory action of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy of Task 7.3 are yearly Science EU Policy Dialogue events. The Europe-LAND project developed the scheme of the Science EU Policy Dialogue as a yearly strategic exchange with high-level EU representatives and complementary EU projects on the policy-making dimension. For the organization and implementation of this action, Europe-LAND is closely collaborating with the two sister projects MOSAIC and PLUS Change. By the time of this report, the projects have hosted two installations of the Science EU Policy Dialogue.

1st Science EU Policy Dialogue – 16.04.2024, 10-12h (CEST), online

The aim of the first installation was to bring together relevant land-use stakeholders from EU projects and EU institutions, to improve the joint understanding of the different perspectives and needs of policy and science. In two co-creation parallel sessions, one for EU projects and one for EU representatives, topics such as upcoming project deliverables with policy relevance, policy needs and open questions from both sides were collected. The format also offered room for an open discussion board, where participants were encouraged to leave open requests for collaboration, or to share their open resources with the group. The event was attended by 50 participants, representing 15 EU projects and 5 EU officials.

2nd Science EU Policy Dialogue – 29.04.2025, 9:30-12h (CEST), online

The second round of the action extended the aim to highlighting in more depth potential contributions of projects in support of the new EU Nature Restoration Law and related EU land use legislation. In two consecutive interactive sessions on land use policy and on land use solutions, the three organizing projects gave flashlight presentations of existing or planned project outcomes and methodologies, inviting participants to open discussions. The event was attended by 67 participants, of which 51 were representatives of EU projects and 16 were EU officials.

National-level Stakeholder Mirror Workshops

In frame of WP3, all project partners organized national stakeholder workshops in their respective countries titled “Present land use and land management challenges and future perspectives”. The aim was to increase stakeholders’ understanding of various key factors contributing to past, present and future land use change. A total of 12 such workshops were organized in 2024. A detailed report of the events was published within the D3.2 Methodological framework “Living Labs” in November 2024. Overall, the workshops reached 601 stakeholders. Table x provides an overview of the hosted workshops.

Table 1. Date and format of the Mirror Workshops in the partners’ countries (see D3.2).

Country	Date	Format	No. of external participants	Observations
Romania	13.06.2024	In-person	21	Europe-LAND event
Germany	01.10.2024	online	7	Europe-LAND event
Portugal	14.10.2024	In-person	13	Europe-LAND event
Latvia	16.10.2024	hybrid	29	Europe-LAND event (session) in the framework of a national conference
Poland	17.10.2024	online	21	Europe-LAND event
Greece	23.10.2024	online	19	Europe-LAND event
Slovakia	10.10., 17.10. 7.11.2024	In-person and hybrid	110+35+75=220	Europe-LAND event expert workshop, seminar with practical demo and national dialogue
Austria	14.,18.10.2024	online	11	Europe-LAND events
Italy	30.10.2024	online	22	Europe-LAND event
Czechia	18.10.2024	online	6	Europe-LAND event
Denmark	9.10.2024	In-person	200	Expert exchanges in the frame of national land-use conference “Fremtidens arealanvendelse (Future land use)” in Aarhus, DK
Estonia	27.11.2024	In-person	32	Europe-LAND event

Online Workshops for raising awareness and best-practice examples

Task 3.5 aims to raise awareness of key stakeholders on climate change and biodiversity challenges and to encourage them to adopt new sustainable practices. Two such online workshops are envisioned over the course of the project.

The first was hosted as an online symposium “**Sustainable Land Use and Land Management: Emerging Trends, Current Challenges, and European Solutions**”, 16th May 2025. In two keynotes and four parallel sessions, 18 experts in the field of land use research presented their work, followed by discussions with participants. The event was attended by 68 participants.

3.2 Press releases, interviews, media articles and TV and radio campaigns

Reaching a broad audience of multiple stakeholder groups at the same time is crucial for the visibility of the project, to raise awareness about the project outcomes. Traditional media channels are an ideal way to reach all stakeholder groups at the same time. This chapter outlines the press releases, interviews, other media articles and TV and radio campaigns facilitated or supported by the Europe-LAND partners over the first two years of the project duration.

Press releases

The project produces and releases at least one official press release per year. The press releases published this far are listed below.

“Research for more sustainable land use and land management in Europe First reflections of the EU-funded research project Europe-LAND”, 08.07.2024, available at:

<https://www.openpr.com/news/3570202/research-for-more-sustainable-land-use-and-land-management>

“Landnutzung: eine Datenbank für den Klimaschutz“, 10.04.2025

Media articles

Besides official press releases published by the project, project partners have also contributed to other media articles with interviews and inputs. Occasionally, project outcomes are picked up by third party publications and disseminated this way. Over the past 24 months, four such other media articles have been published about the Europe-LAND project.

newspaper article, Denmark (UCPH): 02.02.2024, "Emissions from organic wetlands", published in a national Danish newspaper

Target audience: civil society

Status: delivered

interview article published in Hamburg newspaper, Germany (HAW): 27.10.2024, An interview of Franziska Wolf and Jasmin Röseler (HAW) was published in an article by the Bergedorfer Abendblatt, a local Hamburg newspaper

Target audience: citizens

Status: delivered

Interview article on SUA website, Slovakia (SUA): 2024, An interview with Prof. Danka Moravcikova in Slovakian was published on the website of the Slovakian University of Agriculture in Nitra (SUA)

Target audience: research communities

Status: delivered

Article on project workshop, Slovakia (SUA): 2024, An article was published on the university website of SUA, detailing a project workshop

Target audience: research communities

Status: delivered

TV and radio campaigns

TV and radio campaigns are another way to reach a broader audience, who prefer to receive audio and visual information rather than plain text. Europe-LAND partners have contributed to three such outputs over the last 24 months.

Online media and TV, Denmark (UCPH): 11.01.2024 "Emissions from organic wetlands", on the Danish Broadcasting Company

Target audience: civil society

Status: delivered

Radio interview, Denmark (UCPH): 27.06.2024, "Emissions from organic wetlands", on the Danish Broadcasting Company

Target audience: civil society

Status: delivered

Radio interview and podcast "90 seconds of science", Portugal (UC): Interview with the Portuguese project team with the national radio program "90 seconds of science", available as podcast now here: <https://www.90segundosdeciencia.pt/episodes/ep-1836-miguel-moreira/>

Target audience: citizens

Status: delivered

3.3 print materials, videos, podcasts and newsletters

To support communication and the reach of the Europe-LAND project, a coherent project brand consisting of templates and printing materials was produced by the WP7 team. Further communication activities to reach stakeholders from various groups and backgrounds include project videos, a dedicated podcast series and a periodic newsletter. Using multiple medias to communicate project outputs ensures a maximized impact and reach of the project. This section details the aforementioned communication materials produced and disseminated within the first 2 project years.

Print materials

As part of the project brand, various print materials for dissemination have been produced by the project team and used for promotion and dissemination at in-person events. The following print materials have been produced by the project within the first 24 months of the project.

Project poster

A project poster was produced, displaying general information on the project. It is available to all partners to be used for various dissemination activities. It is used at official project events and permanently displayed at the HAW Hamburg project office.

Project roll-up

Similarly to the project poster, a roll-up was produced at HAW Hamburg to be used for promotion of the project at in-person events. The print file is available to all partners for further dissemination work.

Project brochure

A project brochure in English was produced detailing the work plan and giving general information on the project as well as contact information to aid in promoting the project. Further, a template was produced for partners to produce brochures in local languages. The English version was printed 200 times and distributed at project events as well as external in-person events and conferences.

Postcard to promote the Danish Mirror Workshop

The Danish mirror workshop (WP3) was hosted during the Conference "Denmark's land areas - transformation for the future". To promote the workshop, a postcard in print was produced and disseminated at the conference.

Videos

The project team produced **one promotional video** detailing the main focus points of the project. It is available on the project website <https://europe-land.eu/>. Further videos on upcoming project outputs are planned for the second half of the project duration. **A total of four videos** are envisaged by the end of the project. At the time of this report, a second video detailing the Europe-LAND Toolbox was under development. Future videos will also be available on the project website and disseminated over social media.

Podcasts

European Land Use Talks

Within WP7 T7.4, a podcast series of 7 episodes is being produced. Each episode focuses on a specific land-use and project related topic. They will be periodically released around major project outputs, aiming for 3 episodes in 2025 and 2026 and one in 2027.

The first episode, titled "The Vision Behind Europe-LAND – A Conversation with the Coordinator" was published on 7th March 2025 with Podigee, and is available here <https://european-land-use.podigee.io/> as well as on Spotify. It has received 15 downloads since its publication. The next episode is scheduled to be released in June 2025.

Other podcast

Besides the official project podcast series, the SUA project team have contributed to another podcast format with project-related inputs.

Podcast in national language (Slovakian) (SUA)

The need to help raising public awareness on climate change related issues: A podcast prepared with students titled Climate change from the perspective of a sociological survey (in the Slovak language). The SUA team realized a sociological survey (451 questionnaires) to interpret how the Slovak public reflects on the impact of climate change and what is their level of awareness about climate change and related measures and policies. The podcast is divided into 5 thematic parts - Context of public opinion, Climate change, Transformation and Green Deal, Pro-climatic and transformation measures, Climate change narratives. Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qg0Qd1oEdo8>.

Newsletters

In frame of the CDUE-Plan of the project, a periodic newsletter is being produced. A total of 5 newsletters are scheduled to be released over the project duration, with topics closely related to the project.

The first issue of the newsletter was published on 5th December 2024 and was sent out to 413 stakeholders. The issue consisted of 4 articles outlining the ongoing work of the WPs, as well as a short note from each of the two sister projects and announcements for upcoming events. This and all future issues of the newsletter will be available on the project website <https://europe-land.eu/results/>. At the time of this report, issue 2 of the newsletter, with a focus on various forms of stakeholder engagement within the project, is under production and scheduled to be published in early June 2025.

3.5 social media and website

As part of the CDUE-Plan of the project, a broad online presence using a project website and social media was established. A project website and an account on LinkedIn were established by month 6, constituting Milestone 4. An account on X was later created in month 15 to complement the online presence of the project. This chapter details the main activities and achievements of the online presence over the last 24 months.

Website

Serving as a home base for all communications, the website (www.europe-land.eu) is a key channel to communicate project activities to all target audience groups. The website is available in English as well as all 11 partner languages (Czech, Danish, Estonian, German, Greek, Italian, Latvian, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian and Slovakian) to make project outputs more accessible to local stakeholders. Furthermore, HAW Hamburg at the time of this report is working on implementing the requirements of the new EU Accessibility Act, as to make the website more accessible for an even broader audience.

The project website consists of eight sections detailing different aspects of the project. Section one is the 'Home' landing page, displaying an introduction to the project, the first project video and the four most recent news posts and events. The second section, the 'About' tab details the project outline, the project's vision and methodology, the scope of project activities and a map as well as detailed descriptions of the eight case studies. Additionally, the two sister projects are also listed under this tab with links to their official project websites. The 'Partners' tab lists all 13 project partners and two associates with their logo and a link to their official website. The fourth is the 'News' section, where articles about project activities, event recaps, and related topics are published. An internal list for the planning and tracking of the publications in this section is set up in HiDrive within WP7. Within the first 24 months of the project, 30 news posts have been published on the website.

A separate 'Events' section is utilised to announce upcoming events organized by the project. Past events are archived on the website and whenever possible, event material such as agendas and presentations, are made available for download. One of the central sections of the website is the 'Results' tab, on which all public deliverables, scientific publications, and newsletters are made available for download. The section so far contains 7 public deliverables, one newsletter and five scientific publications for download. The deliverable D7.6 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy was delivered in form of a dedicated section on the project website, the seventh section titled 'Join Us'. This section contains a detailed description of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy, all planned participatory actions and easy-to-use forms to sign up to the stakeholder pool and the network of EU projects. The final and newest section of the website is the 'IACS Data Community of Practice'. It details the second Community of Practice of the project, which was established as a result of one of the capacity building seminars organized within WP6 (see chapter 3.1) and provides a form to become a member of the community.

Visitors overall: 3.832

Unique downloads overall: 229

Project LinkedIn account

Launched in June 2023, the Europe-LAND LinkedIn account has 471 followers at the time of submission of this report. It is available here: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/europe-land/>. The page aims to share weekly updates on the project activities and results, events as well as other relevant information on land use in Europe. The platform is ideal to reach relevant stakeholders such as experts from academia and practice as well as professional organizations.

Over the last 24 months, 92 posts have been published on the page, and amassing 687 reactions over the past 12 months.

Audience: 471 followers

Project X account

After initially delaying the establishment of an account on X (see D7.1), the decision was made to open an account in month 15, August 2024, which can be found here: https://x.com/EuropeLAND_EU. The account is used for short announcements of upcoming events and the publication of project outputs. The main stakeholders reached on X are policy officials as well as land users. Over the last 9 months, 11 posts have been published on the page and has gained a small audience of 9 followers.

Audience: 9 followers

Online Forums

Activities of the project were further promoted through the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN) via the Mobilize platform and the SustainChain Platform to the members of SDSN, consisting of researchers from all over the world. AUTH facilitates these efforts.

4. Scientific work

As a research and academia-focused project, scientific work is another vital aspect of how Europe-LAND is disseminating project outcomes. Europe-LAND is committed to sharing project outcomes, whenever possible, as openly and widely as possible. This chapter details the scientific work conducted and published in the frame of the project so far.

4.1 Public deliverables

Within the duration of the project, 26 of the planned deliverables are marked as public, meaning they will be openly available after delivery to the European Commission. Of these, seven are already available by the time of this report. They are available on the project website <https://europe-land.eu/results/> and in the ZENODO community <https://zenodo.org/communities/europeland/>. This report upon delivery will also be made publicly available and constitute the eighth public deliverable.

D2.1 Harmonized database of land use and land management for the entire EU - (M18), downloads from ZENODO: 4.975

D3.2 Methodological framework “Living Labs” – (M18), downloads from ZENODO: 46

D5.1 Report – Telecoupling frameworks – (M12), downloads from ZENODO: 49

D7.1 CDUE-Plan – (M3), downloads from ZENODO: 13

D7.2 CDUE-Plan first update – (M15), downloads from ZENODO: 15

D7.5 Action-Plan for community of Practice – (M9), downloads from ZENODO: 26

D7.6 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy – (M6), downloads from ZENODO: 29

4.2 Scientific publications

Scientific publications in high impacts journals, openly accessible, support the uptake of Europe-LAND data and results for further development of research activities and concrete land use solutions. During the first 24 months of the project, 5 scientific publications were published by Europe-LAND partners.

Schiller, J., Jänicke, C., Reckling, M. & Ryo, M. **Higher crop rotational diversity in more simplified agricultural landscapes in Northeastern Germany.** *Landsc Ecol* 39, 90 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-024-01889-x>

Jänicke, C., Wesemeyer, M., Chiarella, C., Lakes, T., Levers, C., Meyfroidt, P., Müller, D., Pratzner, M. & Rufin, P. **Can we estimate farm size from field size? An empirical investigation of the field size to farm size relationship.** *Agricultural Systems*, 220, 104088 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2024.104088>

Krumins, J., Klavins, M., Stankevica, K. **Implications for conservation zoning in Teici Strict Nature Reserve due to land use and cover change.** *Frontiers in Remote Sensing*, 5:1497454 (2024). doi: 10.3389/frsen.2024.1497454

Kupková, L. & Boudný, Z. **Landscape transformation in Czechia over the last 30 years: diversity of changes on two spatial levels.** *Journal of Maps* (2025). doi: 10.1080/17445647.2025.2468488#d1e223

Krumins, J., Klavins, M. **Scenario-based modelling of land-use and land-cover changes to promote sustainability in biosphere reserves: a case study from North Vidzeme, Latvia.** *Frontiers in Remote Sensing* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsen.2025.1567002>

Hejda T, Kupková L, Boudný Z. **Land use/land cover changes after the decline of mountain chalet farming in the Krkonoše and Hrubý Jeseník Mountains, Czechia, since the mid-20th century.** *Journal of Mountain Science* 22(4), 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11629-024-9143-5>

5. Conclusions

Over the first 24 months of the project, partners have engaged in various activities to disseminate and communicate project outputs and have reached a wide range of stakeholders, specifically from research and academia. Dissemination activities have reached a broad audience and have noted consistently high levels of attendance. Project partners managed to place Europe-LAND at important national and international conferences and events. Communication activities have been equally successful. The digital outreach, consisting of social media, especially LinkedIn, and the website, have managed to create a still growing following with consistent interactions. All proposed events have been implemented, in some cases even going beyond the required frame. Various media channels are being utilized to extend the reach of the project and to bring more attention to project outputs. Scientific work is similarly successful, with a number of scientific publications having been accepted in open access journals and public deliverables being downloaded numerous times.

For the following two years of the project implementation, project partners will continue to engage in dissemination and communication activities. One further deliverable is planned to report in those activities (D7.8, M48).